

Tidal dissipation in rotating low mass stars: implications for the orbital evolution of close in planets

Florian Gallet¹, Emeline Bolmont^{2,3}, Stéphanie Mathis², Corinne Charbonnel^{1,4}, Louis Amard^{1,5}, Yann Alibert⁶

¹ Department of Astronomy, University of Geneva, Chemin des Maillettes 51, 1290 Versoix, Switzerland

² Laboratoire AIM Paris-Saclay, CEA/DRF - CNRS - Univ. Paris Diderot - IRFU/SAP, Centre de Saclay, 91191 Gif-sur-Yvette Cedex, France

³ NaXys, Department of Mathematics, University of Namur, 8 Rempart de la Vierge, 5000 Namur, Belgium ⁴ IRAP, UMR 5277, CNRS and Université de Toulouse, 14 av. E. Belin, 31400 Toulouse, France

⁵ LUPM UMR 5299 CNRS/UM, Université de Montpellier, CC 72, 34095 Montpellier Cedex 05, France

⁶ Physikalisches Institut & Center for Space and Habitability, Universitaet Bern, 3012 Bern, Switzerland

Abstract

Close-in planets represent a large fraction of the population of confirmed exoplanets. To understand the dynamical evolution of these planets, star-planet interactions must be taken into account. In particular, the dependence of the tidal interactions on the structural parameters of the star, its rotation, and its metallicity should be treated in the models. We quantify how the tidal dissipation in the convective envelope of rotating low-mass stars evolves in time. We also investigate the possible consequences of this evolution on planetary orbital evolution. In Gallet *et al.* (2017) and Bolmont *et al.* (2017) we generalized the work of Bolmont & Mathis (2016) by following the orbital evolution of close-in planets using the new tidal dissipation predictions for advanced phases of stellar evolution and non-solar metallicity.

We find that during the pre-main sequence the evolution of tidal dissipation is controlled by the evolution of the internal structure of the star through the stellar contraction. On the main-sequence tidal dissipation is strongly driven by the evolution of the surface rotation that is impacted by magnetized stellar winds braking. Finally, during the more evolved phases, the tidal dissipation sharply decreases as radiative core retreats in mass and radius towards the red-giant branch.

Using an orbital evolution model, we also show that changing the metallicity leads to different orbital evolutions (e.g., planets migrate farther out from an initially fast rotating metal rich star). By using this model, we qualitatively reproduced the observational trends of the population of hot Jupiters with the metallicity of their host stars. However, more work still remain to be done so as to be able to quantitatively fit our results to the observations.

1 Introduction

Thanks to space observatories and to the increase of the precision of modern techniques (e.g. radial velocity and transit methods), we have now access to a huge number of exoplanets that belong to a wide variety of star-planet systems configurations in which host stars are ranging from M red dwarf to intermediate-mass A-type stars (Fabrycky *et al.*, 2014). Among these discovered exoplanets, a fairly large number of them are found close to their host star as it is the case for the well known hot Jupiter's class exoplanet (Mayor & Queloz, 1995; Charbonneau *et al.*, 2000).

The presence of planets is usually not taken into account in the numerical codes dealing with the evolution of stellar rotation (such as angular momentum evolution codes, e.g. Reiners & Mohanty 2012; Gallet & Bouvier 2015; Johnstone *et al.* 2015; Lanzafame & Spada 2015, or stellar evolution codes including angular momentum transport, e.g. Pinsonneault *et al.* 1990; Amard *et al.* 2016; Choi *et al.* 2016). But with the increasing number of detected and confirmed exoplanets, especially the fact that most of them are found close to their host star, star-planet interactions should not be neglected anymore (Strugarek *et al.*, 2014; Strugarek, 2016; Bolmont & Mathis, 2016).

Moreover, observational studies (e.g. Gonzalez, 1997; Santos *et al.*, 2003; Adibekyan *et al.*, 2013) have shown that the exoplanet population depends on the metallicity of the host star. Observational surveys showed that there seems to be more planets around metal-rich stars than around metal poor stars (Gonzalez, 1997; Santos *et al.*, 2003; Neves *et al.*, 2013), that there are fewer small size/low-mass planets around metal-poor stars than around metal-rich stars (Beaugé & Nesvorný, 2013), and that planets between $10 M_{\oplus}$ and $4 M_{\text{JUP}}$ orbiting around metal-poor stars have on average a wider semi-major axis (longer orbital period) than those orbiting metal-rich stars (Adibekyan *et al.*, 2013).

Thanks to recent progress made in the modeling of the dynamical tide induced dissipation occurring in the convective envelope of rotating stars (the frequency-averaged tidal dissipation, which depends on the stellar internal structure properties and surface rotation rate, see Ogilvie, 2013; Mathis, 2015), we could revisit the tidal evolution of close-in planets (Bolmont & Mathis, 2016; Gallet *et al.*, 2017).

In Gallet *et al.* (2017), we primarily investigated the effect of the stellar mass (and thus internal structure) on the frequency-averaged tidal dissipation and modified equivalent tidal quality factor from the pre-main sequence (here-

Figure 1: Stellar evolution tracks in the Hertzsprung-Russell diagram for the rotating models of 0.3, 0.4, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8, 0.9, 1.0, 1.1, 1.2, and 1.4 M_{\odot} at solar metallicity. We show the evolution up to the RGB for the more massive stars or up to the evolution stage the models reach at 20 Gyr for the less massive stars. The symbols represent the first step in each evolution sequence (triangle), the ZAMS (square), and the TAMS (cross). Credit Gallet *et al.* (2017).

after PMS) up to the red-giant branch (hereafter RGB). In Bolmont *et al.* (2017) we investigated the effect of a change of the stellar metallicity both on the frequency-averaged tidal dissipation using the stellar evolution code STAREVOL (e.g. Amard *et al.*, 2016, which includes rotation), and on the resulting tidal orbital evolution of close-in hot Jupiters using the orbital evolution model of Bolmont & Mathis (2016).

This proceeding summarizes the results of these two articles (Gallet *et al.* 2017 and Bolmont *et al.* 2017). A large part of the text of this summary comes from selected passages of each of these papers.

2 Model

2.1 Stellar model

This study is based on a grid of stellar models of rotating stars we computed with the code STAREVOL (see e.g. Amard *et al.*, 2016) for a range of initial masses between 0.3 and 1.4 M_{\odot} at solar metallicity ($Z = 0.0134$; Asplund *et al.* 2009), and for a 0.4 and 1.0 M_{\odot} mass stars at three different metallicities ($Z = 0.004$, $Z = 0.0134$ and $Z = 0.0255$). Figure 1 shows the stellar evolution tracks of the solar metallicity models in the Hertzsprung-Russell diagram.

The references for the basic input micro-physics (equation of state, nuclear reactions, and opacities) can be found in Amard *et al.* (2016) and in Lagarde *et al.* (2012). The initial helium abundance and mixing length parameter are calibrated without atomic diffusion to reproduce a non-rotating Sun with respect to the solar mixture of Asplund *et al.* (2009) with a 10^{-5} precision for the luminosity and the radius at the age of the Sun. The corresponding mixing length parameter and initial helium abundance are $\alpha_{\text{MLT}} = 1.7020$

and $Y = 0.2689$.

2.2 Equilibrium and dynamical tides

In the framework of the tidal interaction and orbital evolution, the tidal dissipation is described by two components: the equilibrium and the dynamical tides. While the equilibrium tides correspond to the large-scale hydro-static readjustment of the star induced by its gravitational interaction with its companion (an another star or a cortege of planets, see Zahn, 1966; Remus *et al.*, 2012); the dynamical tides correspond to the dissipation of tidal inertial waves (mechanical waves that are generated inside rotating fluid bodies) inside the star (Zahn, 1975; Ogilvie & Lin, 2007) by the the convective turbulent friction inside the convective zone of the star, and by the thermal diffusion and breaking mechanisms acting on gravito-inertial waves in the radiative zones (e.g. Zahn, 1975; Terquem *et al.*, 1998; Barker & Ogilvie, 2010).

2.3 Frequency-averaged tidal dissipation

In the formalism of Ogilvie (2013) and Mathis (2015), the stellar convective envelope is assumed to be in solid-body rotation with angular velocity Ω_* . Moderate rotation is assumed, i.e., the squared ratio of Ω_* to the break-up angular velocity Ω_c is such that $(\Omega_*/\Omega_c)^2 = \left(\Omega_*/\sqrt{GM_*/R_*^3}\right)^2 \equiv \epsilon^2 < 1$ (so as to neglect the centrifugal effect), where G is the gravitational constant, and M_* and R_* are the stellar mass and equatorial radius, respectively.

In this mass range explored in this proceeding (0.3-1.4 M_{\odot}), the convective envelope surrounds the radiative core of radius R_c and mass M_c . Both core and envelope are assumed to be homogeneous with respective average densities ρ_c and ρ_e . In the case of a coplanar star-planet system in which the orbit of the planet is circular, the frequency-averaged tidal dissipation (Ogilvie, 2013; Mathis, 2015) is given by:

$$\langle \mathcal{D} \rangle_{\omega} = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \text{Im} [k_2^2(\omega)] \frac{d\omega}{\omega} = f(\epsilon^2)g(\alpha, \beta, \gamma), \quad (1)$$

with

$$\alpha = \frac{R_c}{R_*}, \quad \beta = \frac{M_c}{M_*}, \quad \gamma = \frac{\rho_e}{\rho_c} = \frac{\alpha^3(1-\beta)}{\beta(1-\alpha^3)} < 1. \quad (2)$$

k_2^2 is the Love number of degree 2 corresponding to the quadrupolar mode (k_l^m , with $l = 2$ and $m = 2$ the components of the time-dependent tidal potential proportional to the spherical harmonic Y_l^m) that gives the ratio between the perturbation of the gravitational potential induced by the presence of the planetary companion and the tidal potential evaluated at the stellar surface. Its imaginary component $\text{Im} [k_2^2(\omega)]$ is a direct estimation of the tidal dissipation. The interest of this formalism is that it is possible to decompose Eq. 1 into two parts: the factor $f(\epsilon^2)$ on the one hand, and the part of Eq. 1 that is a unique function of α and β ($g(\alpha, \beta)$) on the other hand. The first part takes into account the rotation rate of the star (via ϵ) and the second part only takes into account the dependence on the internal stellar structure (via the structural parameters α and β , i.e. the radius and mass aspect ratio).

Figure 2: Evolution of the frequency-averaged tidal dissipation $\langle \mathcal{D} \rangle_\omega = \langle \text{Im} [k_2^2(\omega)] \rangle_\omega$, as a function of time for stellar masses (M_\star) from 0.3 to 1.4 M_\odot . Credit Gallet *et al.* (2017).

3 Tidal interaction, internal structure, and rotation rate

We explored the effects of the variations of the stellar rotation rate along the stellar evolution on the dissipation. The surface velocity of our stellar models evolves under the action of the secular variations (expansion and contraction), of magnetic braking, and of internal transport processes. We refer to Amard *et al.* (2016) for details.

Figure 2 shows the evolution of the frequency-averaged tidal dissipation as a function of time. Even if the rotation rate is evolving during the PMS phase it has no impact on the behavior of the tidal dissipation since the rotation itself is entirely controlled by the stellar contraction (i.e. by the internal structure).

During the main-sequence (hereafter MS) phase, both the mass and radius aspect ratios (β and α) remain more or less constant. At that point, the internal structure stops to control the evolution of the tidal dissipation. From the zero-age main sequence (here after ZAMS, ≈ 50 Myr for a $1M_\odot$) and up to the end of the MS phase (hereafter TAMS, for terminal-age main sequence), the tidal dissipation is controlled by the evolution of the surface angular velocity and thus by the extraction of angular momentum by the stellar wind.

Finally, after the TAMS and along the sub-giant and red-giant branch phases, the dissipation first starts to increase and then decreases as both aspect ratios are reduced by the stellar expansion, which leads to a structure that resembles more and more a weakly dissipative fully convective star.

The tidal dissipation is thus strongly affected by the variations of the rotation rate along the evolution of the star.

Figure 3: Frequency-averaged tidal dissipation $\langle \mathcal{D} \rangle_\omega$ as a function of time. The symbol represent: the first step in each model (triangle), ZAMS (square), and TAMS (cross). Credit Bolmont *et al.* (2017).

4 Tidal interaction and metallicity

4.1 Evolution of the frequency-averaged tidal dissipation

When the metallicity of a star of a given mass is reduced, its opacity decreases (due to an easier redistribution of energy inside the star); this leads to a denser and hotter radiative core, and thus to an increase of the luminosity and effective temperature of the star at a given evolution phase. The metallicity of a star is directly linked to the metallicity of its parent molecular cloud. Given this initial amount of foundation bricks, the resulting star-disk systems diversity will range from a massive star surrounded by a thin disk to a low-mass star surrounded by a thick disk. As planets form inside the circumstellar disk, metallicity is also thought to impact their formation and migration processes (e.g. Ida & Lin, 2004; Mordasini *et al.*, 2009; Alibert *et al.*, 2013). Metallicity will then play an important role by indirectly setting the maximum mass of the planets, and possibly impacting also the location of their formation inside the circumstellar disk (e.g. Johnson & Li, 2012; Mordasini *et al.*, 2012). Equation 1 shows that the frequency-averaged tidal dissipation primarily depends on the internal structure of the stars (see Gallet *et al.* 2017 and Bolmont *et al.* 2017 for details). For a given stellar mass, the evolution of the internal structure depends on the initial metallicity. Figure 3 shows the evolution of the frequency-averaged tidal dissipation (see Eq. 1), for the three metallicities considered ($Z=0.004, 0.0134, \text{ and } 0.0255$), as a function of time. Whatever the stellar mass, the general trends which appear when considering different metallicities remain the same. The following description is therefore valid for the $0.4 M_\odot$ star and the $1 M_\odot$ star. Following the evolution of the star, the frequency-averaged tidal dissipation globally decreases when the metallicity is reduced modulo the evolution of the surface rotation of the star.

Figure 4: **Top:** Evolution of the number of planets within a 3-day, 6-day and 10-day orbit for the three different metallicities considered here. **Bottom:** Evolution of the mean orbital period of the simulated planets for the three different metallicities. Credit Bolmont *et al.* (2017).

4.2 Evolution of hot Jupiter’s population

The observations of the population of Hot Jupiters in a orbital period-metallicity diagram displays the two following trends:

- **Trend 1:** the number of massive planets is higher around metal rich stars (Neves *et al.*, 2013),
- **Trend 2:** the massive planets around metal poor stars seem to be on wider orbits than the planets around metal rich stars (Adibekyan *et al.*, 2013).

To study these trends we evolve an initially uniform distribution of hot Jupiter (i.e. uniformly distributed in the $P_{\text{rot}} - P_{\text{orb}}$ plane, and for the three metallicity considered) in time (see Fig. 7 from Bolmont *et al.*, 2017). Figure 4, that shows the evolution of the planet population (top) and mean orbital period as a function of time, summarizes the result we obtained.

Under the hypothesis that there is no particular prior distribution of planets after the formation phases depending on stellar initial periods and metallicities, and that the distribution of stars according to their initial rotation and metallicity period is uniform, the long-term evolution of the population of planets around the metal poor star leads to the following observations (see Fig. 4):

- Around young Sun-like stars (Age < 5 – 6 Gyr), there should be statistically more planets ($P_{\text{orb}} < 10$ days) around metal poor stars than around metal rich stars, and those planets should be located closer;
- Around old Sun-like stars (Age > 5 – 6 Gyr), there should be statistically fewer planets ($P_{\text{orb}} < 10$ days) around metal poor stars than around metal rich stars. For even later ages (Age > 7 Gyr), those planets should be located farther;

We qualitatively reproduce the observational trends of the population of hot Jupiters with the metallicity of their host stars. Namely, we reproduce that for old stars (older than 6 Gyr), the higher the metallicity the higher the number of close-in planets and the higher the metallicity the closer the planets. However, more steps are needed to try to quantitatively fit our results to the observations.

5 Conclusion and perspectives

In Gallet *et al.* (2017) we showed that the tidal dissipation in the convective zones of the stars varies over several orders of magnitudes as a function of the stellar mass, age, and rotation rate. We pointed out the importance of coupling the structural and the rotational evolution when studying the evolution of the orbital evolution of massive close-in planet as a function of time (see Bolmont & Mathis, 2016).

In Bolmont *et al.* (2017) we showed how strong the influence of the stellar metallicity could be on the evolution of the tidal dissipation and thus on the orbital evolution of massive close-in planet. We pointed out that the metallicity effects could explain a part of the observed trend regarding the distribution of hot Jupiter as a function of the metallicity of their host’s star. these results could strongly constrain the initial distribution of hot Jupiters.

With these two papers, we provided the community with new grids of tidal dissipation evolution as a function of the stellar mass and metallicity (grids available here and here).

In the future, we will take into account of the frequency-dependence of the tidal dissipation so as to better describe the orbital evolution of massive close-in planet. We also plan to include the dissipation inside of the radiative zones since for the moment it is only treated inside of the convective envelope.

In the long term we will directly couple the orbital evolution code developed in Bolmont *et al.* (2012) to the STAREVOL code so as to get a real retro-action of the action of the tide on the rotation rate and its feedback effect on the tides.

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